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Primary repair versus colostomy in colonic injuries

Adel Al Rubaee

Simple colonic injuries can often be treated with primary repair. More significant right-sided injuries are often managed by resection with either an ileo-colic or colo-colic anastomosis. Left sided injuries are often treated by resection with either end colostomy or colo-colic anastomosis. We believe that primary repair can safely be performed more frequently than generally accepted.

120 cases of penetrating injuries were observed over period of (3) years from March 2003 to March 2006. The patients were admitted in Balad, Al-Noor and Al-Kadhimiya Teaching hospitals. Most of them were caused by high velocity missiles or fragmentation missiles, some caused by low velocity missiles. Colonic injuries were detected by by general examination, rectal examination, sigmoidoscopy and abdominal X-rays. Their age ranged from 5 to 55 years. Most patients reached hospital from 1/2 hours to 3 hours after the injury. 30 patients (25%) reached hospital in shock state. In 85 cases (70.8%) the injury involved the left colon and in the remaining 35 (29.2%) the right colon

In 60 cases there was single perforation, in 20 cases (16.6%) there were two perforations and in the remaining 40 patients (33.4%) there were multiple perforations of colon. 95 patients (79.2%) had associated non-colonic intra abdominal injuries and 25 patients (20.8%) had isolated colonic injury. Associated injuries of the small bowel occurred in 45 patients (47.3%), in the liver in 15 patients (15.8%), in the spleen in 12 patients (12.6%), in the stomach in 9 patients (9.5%), in the kidney in 8 patients (8.4%). While vascular injuries occurred in 6 patients (6.4%). Complications including wound infection, intra abdominal abscess, and fistula occurred in 32 patients. 15 patients died (12.5%). The death in 11 patients was due to severe associated injuries. Colon-related deaths occurred in 4 patients (3.3%) due to post-operative enteric fistula or leak and intra abdominal sepsis. Injuries of right colon treated by primary repair had the same morbidity as the ones in left colon treated similarly, and both patient part of colon had similar complication rates when the colostomy was performed. Shock on admission is generally considered a contra-indication to primary repair unless it is treated aggressively.

Thirty five patients were treated with primary repair after debridement when necessary. Eighty five patients were treated with colostomy proximal to or at site of perforation. The incidence of

Adel Al Rubaee

Specialist Surgeon
University Hospital in Al Kadhimiya
Baghdad, Iraq

complications in patients treated by colostomy was higher than that one treated by primary repair ((29.4%) versus (20%).Complications occurred in 25.7% of patients with right colonic injuries, and 27% of patients with left colon injuries. The hospital stay of patients treated by primary closure was 10 days and in those treated by colostomy 14 days.

Although colostomy is considered the safest method of treatment of colonic injuries, we believe that colostomy has been over used .Colostomy associated with higher incidence of wound sepsis and intra peritoneal abscess because its considered as an open source of contamination ,very close to the abdominal incision and communication with the abdominal cavity through abdominal wall exist .It is associated with longer hospital stay than after primary repair and the patient have to be subjected to the risk of another operation for closure of colostomy.